

Systematic organization of COVID-19 data supported by the Adverse Outcome Pathway framework

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Abstract

The 2019 coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19) engages a large number of scientists across the world. Literature and data are emerging quickly and is made openly available to support reuse. This enormous worldwide joint research effort on one specific disease provides us with a unique opportunity to map and understand human biology and response to virus infection. However, the immense amounts of information and big data are difficult to handle and systematically review. A common basis and infrastructure for collaboration across various disciplines is needed. The Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) framework was developed to provide a means for interdisciplinary and systematic gathering, organization and review of highly variable types of available data and information. The framework has, to date, mainly been applied within the field of toxicology and chemical risk assessment, but due to its central conceptual principles and guidelines, it is widely applicable to any medical field associated with the need for elucidating underlying mechanisms of disease. This talk will outline newly initiated efforts to streamline collaboration between scientists across the world towards development of AOPs for COVID-19.